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**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

Deliverable of the MINOTAUR project
D#-WP4.1

Database including data and metadata from LTEs,
incubations under controlled conditions
in relation to climate change scenarios and
chronosequences

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Deliverable 4.1 Database including data and metadata from LTEs, incubations under controlled conditions in relation to climate change scenarios and chronosequences

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Table of Contents

List of Tables.....	4
List of Figures	5
List of acronyms and abbreviations.....	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Metadata from Long Tem Experiments (LTEs) (Task 4.1)	7
2.1. Soil biological indicators	10
2.1.1. Microbiota	10
2.1.2. Microfauna	11
2.1.3. Mesofauna.....	12
2.1.4. Macrofauna	13
2.2. Soil functions	14
2.2.1. Regulation of soil organic carbon and nutrients.....	14
2.2.2. Regulation of water	16
2.2.3. Disease suppression	17
3. Metadata from Incubation Experiments (Task 4.2)	17
4. Metadata from chronosequence study (Task 4.3).....	18
List of references.....	19

List of Tables

Table 1. LTEs selected for Task 4.1 and their experimental design: Fertilization treatments include mineral (MN), organic (OG) and non-fertilized (NF). Cultivation treatments include Standard or conventional tillage (ST), reduced tillage (RT) and no tillage or direct seeding (NT).	8
Table 2. Metadata collated for the selected LTEs.....	8
Table 3. Microbiota indicators estimated in MINOTAUR LTEs samples.....	10
Table 4. Microfauna indicators estimated in MINOTAUR LTEs samples.....	11
Table 5. Mesofauna indicators estimated in MINOTAUR LTEs samples	12
Table 6. Macrofauna indicators estimated in MINOTAUR LTEs samples	13
Table 7. Indicators estimated in MINOTAUR LTEs samples related to the regulation of soil organic carbon and nutrients.....	14
Table 8. Indicators estimated in MINOTAUR LTEs samples related to the soil water regulation function	16
Table 9. Variables used to estimate soils disease suppression capacity from MINOTAUR LTEs samples	17

Table 10. Variables generated from the MINOTAUR incubation study	17
Table 11. Variables generated from the MINOTAUR chronosequence study.....	19

List of Figures

Figure 1. General approach of WP4 to obtain empirical measurements of soil biodiversity indicator and soil functions under various context scenarios.	6
Figure 2. Location of the MINOTAUR participant countries and selected LTEs Part.....	7
Figure 3. Summary of the sampling scheme. Composite samples were composed of five subsamples mixed into a composite sample per plots. Soil blocks and infiltration were sampled at one sampling location per plot.	10
Figure 4. Description of the Sampling design adapted from the LUCAS protocols (Fernández-Ugalde et al 2018)	9
Figure 5. Scheme of biodiversity indicators and ecosystem functions assessed for each LTE and treatment. The project partner conducting the analyses is indicated in brackets.	9
Figure 6. CREA pedotheque – Fagna (Italy), used for the MINOTAUR chronosequence study.....	19
Figure 7 General view of the data flow with Open ADOM	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 8. The data flow from the owner to the user	Error! Bookmark not defined.

List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
LTEs	Long-Term Experiments

1. Introduction

The objective of Work Package 4 (WP4) within the MINOTAUR project is to validate selected soil biodiversity indicators and models, examining their sensitivity and ranges concerning soil type, climate, and management practices—collectively referred to as “context scenarios.” By addressing these variables, WP4 aims to fill existing knowledge gaps, gather additional information on specific understudied parameters, and validate the indicators identified in Work Package 3 (WP3) and provide data to parameterize and validate models developed in Work Package 5 (WP5). This will be achieved through targeted measurements and new empirical data obtained from three primary sources: **Long-Term Experiments (LTEs) (Task 4.1)**, **laboratory incubations (Task 4.2)**, and **archived chronosequences (Task 4.3)** (Figure 1). The simultaneous analysis of biodiversity indicators and functions under identical scenarios will enhance our understanding of the covariation between diversity and function, potentially leading to the development of novel multi-taxa indicators.

The impetus for WP4 stems from previous and ongoing initiatives, such as those by Orgiazzi et al. (2016), the Global Soil Biodiversity Initiative (Guerra et al., 2020), and activities within the EJP-SOIL program (Pavlu et al., 2021). These efforts have identified commonly used indicators for soil biodiversity; however, the variability and ranges of these indicators in relation to climate, soil types, and soil management practices remain insufficiently understood. Additionally, the relationships between biodiversity, soil functioning, and ecosystem services across varying European edaphoclimatic and management gradients have yet to be comprehensively elucidated (Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2020).

Figure 1. General approach of WP4 to obtain empirical measurements of soil biodiversity indicator and soil functions under various context scenarios.

2. Metadata from Long Tem Experiments (LTEs) (Task 4.1)

Minotaur's Task 4.1. *Field assessment of soil biodiversity indicators and functions on selected LTEs* aimed to asses a comprehensive list of bioindicators (both taxonomical and functional) and related soil functions on selected LTEs under a range of specific contextual scenarios. The selected LTEs (Figure 2) have been running by consortium partner institutions for more than a decade and include a minimum of three randomized blocks. In total, we selected **9 LTEs from eight countries**, including Spain, France, Italy, Slovenia, Austria, Switzerland, The Netherlands, and Sweden (Figure 2). All experiments asses the effects of minimizing soil disturbance by comparing standard tillage vs. reduced or no-tillage and/or implementing distinct fertilization approaches (mineral vs. organic amendments) (**Error! Reference source not found.**). The metadata collated for these LTEs are presented in Table 2

Figure 2. Location of the MINOTAUR participant countries and selected LTEs Part

Table 1. LTEs selected for Task 4.1 and their experimental design: Fertilization treatments include mineral (MN), organic (OG) and non-fertilized (NF). Cultivation treatments include Standard or conventional tillage (ST), reduced tillage (RT) and no tillage or direct seeding (NT).

LET - Experimental site	Country	Partner	Fertilization			Cultivation		
			MN	OG	NF	ST	RT	NT
SOERE-PRO-EFELE-TS-MO	France	ACO	X	X		X	X	
FAST	Switzerland	AGS	X	X		X	X	
Hollabrunn	Austria	BOKU	X			X	X	X
Fagna	Italy	CREA	X			X	X	
La Canaleja	Spain	INIA	X	X		X	X	X
Uppsala research station (Säby)	Sweden	SLU	X			X	X	X
Lanna research station	Sweden	SLU	X	X	X	X		
TillComp (Ljubljana)	Slovenia	ULBF	X	X	X	X		X
BASIS	Netherlands	WUR	X			X	X	X

Table 2. Metadata collated for the selected LTEs

Variable name	Description
<i>Year start experiment</i>	The year the experiment started
<i>Soil type</i>	The soil type according the World Reference Base for soil resources (WRB).
<i>Texture</i>	Indicate the texture of the soil : Sand, Loamy sand, Sandy loam, Sandy clay loam, Silt loam, Silty clay loam, Loam, Fine sand
<i>Crop rotations</i>	The types of crop within the rotation
<i>Crop residue</i>	If the crop residue is removed or left on site or incorporated into the soil
<i>Fertilizer type</i>	The type of mineral/ organic fertilizer used (e.g. cattle manure, pig slurry)
<i>Fertilization amount</i>	The amount of fertilizer used per ha
<i>Pest control Type</i>	If pest control (Glyphosate) was used
<i>Tillage method</i>	The tillage method. Includes: Mouldboard ploughing, No tillage, disk harrow, chisel plow, cultivator
<i>Tillage depth</i>	Tillage depth in cm
<i>Longitude</i>	Coordinates of the LTE
<i>Latitude</i>	Coordinates of the LTE
<i>Altitude</i>	Elevation of the LTE
<i>Mean climate conditions</i>	Averages min, max temperatures and accumulated precipitation (annual and monthly)

A comprehensive list of biodiversity and soil function variables (Figure 3) to be estimated at each LTE was defined by the project partners. Soil samples were extracted according to a common protocol that specified the location, depth and method for the soil extraction as well as the storage conditions (Figure 4, Figure 5). Samples were then exchanged among project partners who conducted the analyses.

Figure 3. Scheme of biodiversity indicators and ecosystem functions assessed for each LTE and treatment. The project partner conducting the analyses are indicated in brackets.

Figure 4. Description of the Sampling design adapted from the LUCAS protocols (Fernández-Ugalde et al 2018)

Figure 5. Summary of the sampling scheme. Composite samples were composed of five subsamples mixed into a composite sample per plots. Soil blocks and infiltration were sampled at one sampling location per plot.

2.1. Soil biological indicators

2.1.1. Microbiota

The microbiota sampling was conducted following the LUCAS scheme, with five sub-sampling points (centre, N, E, S, W). A soil sample (0-10 cm, approximately 400g) was taken using a spade or trowel. The subsamples were gently mixed and an aliquot was frozen as soon as possible; Frozen samples were shipped to CZU for DNA extraction, CEBAS-CSIC for determination of microbial biomass, and basal respirations, WUR for ergosterol. DNA bioinformatics were conducted by CZU, whereas quantitative PCR was conducted by CEBAS-CSIC. The variables derived from the microbiota sampling are included in Table 3.

Table 3. Microbiota indicators estimated in MINOTAUR LTEs samples

Variables	Method
Microbial biomass	
<i>Fungal ergosterol</i>	µg ergosterol/g moist soil . De Ridder-Duine et al. 2006.
<i>Bacterial Biomass</i>	nmol FAME g ⁻¹ soil . Fatty acid methyl ester

<i>Fungal Biomass</i>	nmol FAME g ⁻¹ soil . Fatty acid methyl ester
<i>Basal soil respiration</i>	µg C-CO ₂ soil g ⁻¹ day ⁻¹ . Infrared CO ₂ analyzer
Microbial functional genes	
<i>16S rRNA gene</i>	quantitative PCR .Primers: Eub338 (Forward) and Eub518 (Reverse)
<i>phoD gene</i>	quantitative PCR Primers: ALPS-F730 (F) and ALPS-R1101 (R)
<i>gcd gene</i>	quantitative PCR .Primers: Gcd-F (F) and Gcd_R (R)
<i>amoA_bac gene</i>	quantitative PCR . Bacterial amoA gene. Primers: AmoA1F (F) and AmoA2R (R)
<i>amoA_arc gene</i>	quantitative PCR . Archaeal amoA gene. Primers: Arch-amoAF (F) and Arch-amoAR (R)
<i>nirS gene</i>	quantitative PCR . Primers: nirSCd3aF (F) and nirSR3cd (R)
Microbial taxonomy	
<i>16S taxonomy</i>	Illumina Reads
<i>18S Taxonomy</i>	Illumina Reads

2.1.2. Microfauna

Microfauna samples were obtained following the same procedure of composite sub-samples defined for microbiota. Microfauna samples were kept cool (4C) and shipped to SLW (Sweden), where nematode community was extracted and then functionally and taxonomically identified. The variables derived from the microbiota sampling are included in Table 4Table 3

Table 4. Microfauna indicators estimated in MINOTAUR LTEs samples

Variable	Description
<i>Total nematode abundance</i>	Abundances are given as number of individuals per 100 g dry soil.
<i>Abundance by functional group</i>	Herbivores, Fungivores, Bacterivores, Predators, Omnivores
<i>Abundance per family</i>	Tylenchidae, Dolichodoridae, Hoplolaimidae, Pratylenchidae, Heteroderidae, Criconematidae, Paratylenchidae, Anguinidae, Aphelenchidae, Aphelenchoididae, Rhabditidae, Cephalobidae, Osstellidae, Panagrolaimidae, Monhysteridae, Plectidae, Diplopeltidae, Achromadoridae, Bastianiidae, Pristomatolaimidae, Tripylidae, Alaimidae, Mononchidae, Anatonchidae, Nygolaimidae, Thornenematidae, Nordiidae, Qudsianematidae, Aporcelaimidae, Belonidiridae, Discolaimidae, Leptonchidae, Diphtherophoridae.
<i>Maturity Index</i>	The maturity index (MI) is a measure of environmental disturbance based on the composition of non-plant parasitic nematode species.
<i>Maturity Index 2-5</i>	Similar to MI but only nematodes with c-p value 2-5 are included (MI 2-5).

<i>Sigma Maturity Index</i>	Both non-plant parasitic and plant parasitic nematodes combined in one index (Sigma MI).
<i>Plant-parasitic index</i>	The plant-parasitic index (PPI) indicates the maturity of the root-feeding nematode community determined by the vigour of their host plants which, in turn, is determined by system enrichment.
<i>Channel Index</i>	The channel index (CI) is an indicator of the predominant decomposition pathways (bacteria or fungi).
<i>Enrichment Index</i>	The enrichment index (EI) is based on the abundance of enrichment opportunists that arise from decomposition of organic matter content and assesses food web responses to available resources.
<i>Structure Index</i>	The structure index (SI) indicates the level of food web complexity and decreases rapidly in response to disturbance.

2.1.3. Mesofauna

The mesofauna sampling protocol for the Minotaur project involved systematic collection and extraction procedures to ensure reliable and consistent data. Sampling was conducted in three plots per treatment, choosing a central point in each plot (LUCAS point), located at least 5 meters from the plot margins. Above-ground plant cover and top litter were gently removed to expose the soil surface. A 10x10 cm undisturbed soil sample, extending 10 cm deep, was extracted using a spade or trowel and placed into a labeled plastic bag, retaining at least 30% of the air volume. Samples were stored at approximately 20°C to prevent thermal shocks. These samples were transported to the laboratory for extraction within 48 hours.

The method for extracting mesofauna involved using a Berlese-Tullgren Funnel, which utilizes a heat gradient to drive the organisms into vials at the bottom of the funnel. The extraction process required a separate funnel for each sample and lasted between 5 to 15 days, depending on the initial soil humidity. Soil samples were weighed before and after extraction, and the extracted mesofauna were collected in vials containing a preservative mixture of 75% ethanol and 25% glycerol. Mesofauna samples were shipped to CREA for identification. The variables derived from the mesofauna sampling are included in Table 5.

Table 5. Mesofauna indicators estimated in MINOTAUR LTEs samples

Variable	Description
<i>QBS-ar</i>	qbs ar index based on the sample (https://zenodo.org/records/7778672)
<i>QBS-ar_BF</i>	qbs ar BF index based on the sample (https://zenodo.org/records/7778672)
<i>Spectral_analysis</i>	(https://zenodo.org/records/7778672)
<i>Variability_replicates</i>	variability of QBS AR among replicates (https://zenodo.org/records/7778672)
<i>Number of forms by type - qbs ar index</i>	Eudaphic, Emiedaphic, Epigeic

<i>Number of forms by type - qbs BF index</i>	Eudaphic, Emiedaphic, Epigeic
<i>QBS-ar_BF_rep</i>	partial qbs- ar biological form, based on the replicate
<i>Number of individuals by taxa and size</i>	Acari, Araneae, Pseudoscorp., Opiliones, Palpigradi, Isopoda, Symphyla, Diplopoda, Chilopoda, Pauropoda, Collembola, Diplura, Protura, Coleoptera, Coleoptera-L, Diptera, Diptera-L, Hymenoptera, Hymenoptera-L, Hemiptera, Psocoptera, Thysanoptera, Embioptera, Dermaptera,

2.1.4. Macrofauna

The macrofauna sampling protocol included both physical and chemical extraction methods to ensure comprehensive collection of earthworms and other macrofauna. In the field, three sampling spots were selected within each plot. The physical extraction involved defining a 20x20 cm sampling zone, from which a soil block (0-20 cm depth) was quickly excavated using a spade. The soil block, including any remaining soil at the bottom of the hole, was collected in a plastic bucket or tray. The soil was then spread out on a plastic sheet or in a second bucket, and earthworms were hand-sorted by crumbling the soil clods.

Simultaneously, a chemical extraction was conducted by applying 500 ml of a mustard solution (30g of mustard powder per liter of water) into the hole left by the soil block extraction. The solution was added in two steps: first, 250 ml, followed by another 250 ml if the initial application infiltrated. Earthworms emerging from the mustard solution were collected in a pillbox containing 99% ethanol. This process was monitored alongside the hand sorting, with mustard extraction continuing for 30 minutes after the last application. Any other macrofauna specimens encountered were collected into a separate pillbox.

The collected specimens were sent to ACO Agrocapus (France) for taxonomic and functional determination. The variables derived from the macrofauna sampling are included in Table 6.

Table 6. Macrofauna indicators estimated in MINOTAUR LTEs samples

Variable	Description
<i>Number of earthworms individuals per m2</i>	total and by functional group (epigeic, stric anecic, anecid, epianecid, endogeic, intermediate)
<i>Biomass of earthworms per m2</i>	total and by functional group (epigeic, stric anecic, anecid, epianecid, endogeic, intermediate)
<i>Earthworm richness</i>	Total number of earthworm species per m2
<i>Earthworm diversity</i>	Shannon index of earthworms

<i>Abundance of key taxons per m²</i>	Eisenia, Eiseniella, Dendrobaena, Dendrodrilus, Lumbricus, Fitzingeria, Aporrectodea, Scherotheca, Octodrilus, Octodrilus, Hormogaster, Allolobophora, Octolasion, Avelona, Ethnodrilus, Proctodrilus, Proselodrilus, Orodrilus, Microscolex, Pontodrilus, Hemigastrodrilus, Miroscolex.
<i>Biomass of key taxons per m²</i>	Eisenia, Eiseniella, Dendrobaena, Dendrodrilus, Lumbricus, Fitzingeria, Aporrectodea, Scherotheca, Octodrilus, Octodrilus, Hormogaster, Allolobophora, Octolasion, Avelona, Ethnodrilus, Proctodrilus, Proselodrilus, Orodrilus, Microscolex, Pontodrilus, Hemigastrodrilus, Miroscolex.
<i>Occurence of key taxons per m²</i>	Eisenia, Eiseniella, Dendrobaena, Dendrodrilus, Lumbricus, Fitzingeria, Aporrectodea, Scherotheca, Octodrilus, Octodrilus, Hormogaster, Allolobophora, Octolasion, Avelona, Ethnodrilus, Proctodrilus, Proselodrilus, Orodrilus, Microscolex, Pontodrilus, Hemigastrodrilus, Miroscolex.

2.2. Soil functions

2.2.1. Regulation of soil organic carbon and nutrients

Indicators related to the regulation of soil organic carbon and nutrients were assessed in the same composite samples as microbiota and microfauna. Soil samples were kept cool (4C) and shipped to MBG-CSIC (Spain) for analyses. The indicators for the regulation of soil organic carbon and nutrients are included in Table 7Table 4Table 3

Table 7. Indicators estimated in MINOTAUR LTEs samples related to the regulation of soil organic carbon and nutrients

Variable	Description
Main physico-chemical properties	
<i>pH H₂O</i>	1:2.5 soil:solution ratio
<i>pH KCl</i>	1:2.5 soil:solution ratio
<i>Total C</i>	Elemental analyser (Carlo Erba, Milan, Italy).
<i>Total organic C</i>	Elemental Analyser (Carlo Erba, Milan, Italy) after CaCO ₃ removal by the "capsule method" using 20% HCl (Brodie et al., 2011)
<i>Total N</i>	Elemental analyser (Carlo Erba, Milan, Italy).
<i>d¹³C</i>	Isotopic Ratio Mass Spectrometer Finnigan Mat Delta C, coupled online to an Elemental Analyser Carlo Erba 1508
<i>d¹⁵N</i>	Isotopic Ratio Mass Spectrometer Finnigan Mat Delta C, coupled online to an Elemental Analyser Carlo Erba 1509
<i>C/N</i>	Elemental analyser (Carlo Erba, Milan, Italy).

<i>Lábile C</i>	Extractable with hot water (Sparling et al., 1998; Ghani et al., 2003) and determination of non-purgable organic carbon (NPOC) by TOC
<i>Sand</i>	International pipette method, after destruction OM with H ₂ O ₂ (Gee & Bauder, 1986)
<i>Clay</i>	International pipette method, after destruction OM with H ₂ O ₂ (Gee & Bauder, 1986)
<i>Silt</i>	International pipette method, after destruction OM with H ₂ O ₂ (Gee & Bauder, 1986)
<i>Texture</i>	USDA (2014)
Enzymatic activities	
<i>Dehydrogenase</i>	µmol INTF g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ ; Camiña et al. (1998)
<i>Urease</i>	µmol NH ₃ g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ ; Nannipieri et al. (1980)
<i>Arylsulphatase</i>	µmol p-nitrophenol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ . Tabatabai and Bremner (1970) with modifications (García et al., 2003 or Trasar-Cepeda et al., 2008)
<i>Acid and alkaline phosphomonoesterase</i>	µmol p-nitrophenol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ pH variable, depending on the samples (acid around 5, alkaline around 10.5) as Tabatabai and Bremner (1969) with modifications (García et al., 2003 or Trasar-Cepeda et al., 2008)
<i>β-glucosidase</i>	µmol p-nitrophenol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ Tabatabai and Bremner (1970) with modifications (García et al., 2003 or Trasar-Cepeda et al., 2008)
Bioavailable macronutrients	
<i>Available Pi</i>	Extractable with sodium bicarbonate 0.5 M, pH 8.5, Hedley et al (1982), determination of P in the extracts following Davidescu and Davidescu (1982) and determination of P by molibdenum-ascorbic acid method (Murphy and Riley, 1962)
<i>Labile Po</i>	Extractable with sodium bicarbonate 0.5 M, pH 8.5, Hedley et al (1982), determination of P in the extracts following Davidescu and Davidescu (1982) and determination of P by molibdenum-ascorbic acid method (Murphy and Riley, 1962)
<i>Available NH₄-N</i>	Extractable with KCl 2 M (1:5 soil:solution ratio), determination by microdiffusion method
<i>Available NO₃-N</i>	Extractable with KCl 2 M (1:5 soil:solution ratio), determination by microdiffusion method
Macro and micronutrients	
<i>Calcium</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.
<i>Cobalt</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.
<i>Copper</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.
<i>Iron</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.
<i>Potassium</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.
<i>Magnesium</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.
<i>Manganes</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.
<i>Nickel</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.
<i>Phosphorus</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.
<i>Lead</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.
<i>Zinc</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.

<i>Aluminium</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.
<i>Cromium</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.
<i>Cadmium</i>	Acid digestion (HNO:HCl 3:1), microwave, ICP-OES.

2.2.2. Regulation of water

The ecosystem function ‘regulation of water’ was assessed using two types of indicators: Soil aggregate stability variables and infiltration rate.

The soil aggregates sampling protocol focused measuring soil structure and stability accurately. Since soil stability does not exhibit significant spatial variability, a single soil sample per plot was deemed sufficient. Each sample was collected as a soil block approximately 20x20x10 cm in size, that was kept in a tight container and shipped to ACO (France) for the determination of various measurements. Soil aggregate stability was measured as described by Le Bissonnais (1996) to distinguish different breakdown mechanisms

The infiltration rate sampling protocol followed the ring method where a ring was inserted into the soil to a depth of 2-3 cm to prevent lateral water loss. A fixed volume of water, corresponding to 1 cm water knife (approximately 700 cm³), was poured into the ring at time zero, and the time taken for this volume to infiltrate was measured. Once the first volume had infiltrated, additional known volumes of water were added sequentially, and the infiltration time for each was recorded. This process was repeated for about 8 to 10 volumes. The variables associated to the water regulation function are included in Table 8.

Table 8. Indicators estimated in MINOTAUR LTEs samples related to the soil water regulation function

Variable	Description
Aggregate stability	
<i>Fast wetting test</i>	fast wetting test (emphasizes the slaking mechanism and reflects the break-down caused by the compression of entrapped air during wetting - it reflects soil stability against a heavy raining event)
<i>Mechanical breakdow test</i>	mechanical breakdown (simulating a raindrop impact on wet soil - wet mechanical cohesion of aggregates independently of slaking)
<i>Slow wetting test</i>	slow wetting test (reflecting the breakdown of aggregates by micro cracking corresponding to wetting by gentle rain)
<i>Mean aggregate stability</i>	mean of the 3 tests
Infiltration	
<i>Infiltration rate</i>	Rate of water infiltration in soil in cm/h
<i>Bulk density</i>	Bulk density measured in g/cm ³ from top 10 cm

2.2.3. Disease suppression

Soils capacity for disease suppression was assessed in the same composite samples as microbiota and micro fauna and soil chemical properties. Soil samples were kept cool (4C) and shipped to WUR (The Netherlands) for analyses. The indicators used to estimate soil's capacity for disease suppression are included in Table 9. Table 7 Table 4 Table 3

Table 9. Variables used to estimate soils disease suppression capacity from MINOTAUR LTEs samples

Variable	Description
Natural percentage of disease	percentage disease, without the addition of Pythium (=natural infection)
Natural fresh biomass	gram per pot aboveground fresh biomass, without the addition of Pythium (=natural infection)
Infected percentage of disease	percentage disease, with the addition of Pythium
Infected fresh biomass	gram per pot aboveground fresh biomass, with the addition of Pythium

3. Metadata from Incubation Experiments (Task 4.2)

In Task 4.2, *Quantify soil biodiversity indicators variability and resilience under controlled climate change conditions*, a soil incubation experiment under controlled conditions has been conducted to monitor selected microbial compositional and functional bioindicators aiming to establish their sensitivity to climate change scenarios. Soils from three Long-Term Experiments (LTEs) located in Switzerland, France, and Spain, representing a gradient of climatic conditions across northern, central, and southern Europe, were used in this experiment. The experimental design in these sites includes soils subjected to various treatments (mineral standard tillage, mineral reduced/non-tillage, organic reduced tillage) with three replicates per treatment at each site, totalling 60 microcosms.

These soils were collected simultaneously with those from Task 4.1 and sent to the labs at CEBAS-CSIC and MBG-CSIC for analysis. The water holding capacity and textural properties of the soils were estimated to determine specific incubation conditions. Soils were moistured and subjected to drying (air conditions) during 40 days. The objective was to assess how agricultural management determine the resistance of the soil microbial community against Climate change factors, in this case, drought. Other variables determined are included in Table 10.

Table 10. Variables generated from the MINOTAUR incubation study

Variables	Method
Microbial biomass	
<i>Bacterial Biomass</i>	nmol FAME g ⁻¹ soil . Fatty acid methyl ester

<i>Fungal Biomass</i>	nmol FAME g ⁻¹ soil . Fatty acid methyl ester
<i>Basal soil respiration</i>	µg C-CO ₂ soil g ⁻¹ day ⁻¹ . Infrared CO ₂ analyzer
Microbial taxonomy	
<i>16S taxonomy</i>	Illumina Reads
<i>18S Taxonomy</i>	Illumina Reads
Physico-chemical properties	
<i>Lábile C</i>	Extractable with hot water (Sparling et al., 1998; Ghani et al., 2003) and determination of non-purgable organic carbon (NPOC) by TOC
<i>Water field capacity</i>	Water field capacity at 10.13 kPa (pF = 2) in a Richard's membrane-plate extractor
Enzymatic activities	
<i>Dehydrogenase</i>	µmol INTF g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ ; Camiña et al. (1998)
<i>Urease</i>	µmol NH ₃ g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ ; Nannipieri et al. (1980)
<i>Arylsulphatase</i>	µmol p-nitrophenol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ . Tabatabai and Bremner (1970) with modifications (García et al., 2003 or Trasar-Cepeda et al., 2008)
<i>Acid and alkaline phosphomonoesterase</i>	µmol p-nitrophenol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ pH variable, depending on the samples (acid around 5, alkaline around 10.5) as Tabatabai and Bremner (1969) with modifications (García et al., 2003 or Trasar-Cepeda et al., 2008)
<i>β-glucosidase</i>	µmol p-nitrophenol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ Tabatabai and Bremner (1970) with modifications (García et al., 2003 or Trasar-Cepeda et al., 2008)

4. Metadata from chronosequence study (Task 4.3)

In Task 4.3, *Assessment of temporal dynamics of soil biodiversity on chronosequences*, approximately 50 samples from soil chronosequences were utilized to assess soil biodiversity sensitivity to climate and agricultural management over time (Figure 6). This is achieved through PCR-based approaches (DNA metabarcoding and qPCR) and enzymatic activity analyses on both frozen and dried soil samples. Samples collected in 2011 and 2022 from two Long-Term Experiments (LTEs) in Italy and Slovenia, where 2 treatments, standard tillage and reduced tillage, were implemented. Samples have been stored as both frozen (-20°C) and air-dried samples, allowing for a comparison that will help identify the potential of these methods for long term storage and retrospective analysis of biodiversity. Lab work included DNA extraction and sequencing of 16S gene and qPCR from soil samples (Table 11).

Figure 6. CREA pedothèque – Fagna (Italy), used for the MINOTAUR chronosequence study.

Table 11. Variables generated from the MINOTAUR chronosequence study

Variables	Method
Microbial functional genes	
<i>16S rRNA gene</i>	Total number of copies: Yield and quality
<i>aprA gene</i>	quantitative PCR - sulfate reduction and sulfur oxidation
<i>nosZ gene</i>	quantitative PCR - Denitrification
<i>nifH gene</i>	quantitative PCR - Nitrogen fixation
Microbial taxonomy	
<i>16S taxonomy</i>	Number of reads per ASV/ Taxa
<i>Richness</i>	Number of ASV
<i>Shannon diversity</i>	Diversity of ASV
<i>Evenness</i>	Distribution of ASV relative abundances

5. Data repository

Data will be made available in an open permanent repository ZENODO under the community MINOTAUR <https://zenodo.org/communities/minotaur>. Data will follow the FAIR principles: Findable, Interoperable, Accessible and Reusable. Datasets will have their own DOI, which will be referenced in scientific publications, under a CC BY license (open with recognition of authorship). Data will become available at the end of the project, respecting an embargo period to get results published. Intellectual property rights will be respected.

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